

STAGES OF UZBEK LITERARY CRITICISM

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Abstract. *Uzbek literary criticism has its own historical development. Active mainly in the 20th century, this field has appeared in various phases. The article gives opinions on the formation and history of literary criticism.*

Key words: *history of literary criticism, stages of development, press, early samples, public consciousness.*

ЭТАПЫ УЗБЕКСКОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРНОЙ КРИТИКИ

Аннотация. *Узбекское литературоведение имеет свое историческое развитие. Эта область, активно действовавшая в основном в 20 веке, появлялась на разных этапах. В статье приводятся мнения о становлении и истории литературной критики.*

Ключевые слова: *история литературоведения, этапы развития, пресса, ранние образцы, общественное сознание.*

INTRODUCTION

From time immemorial, in the works of each creator, in a sense, literary critical views are reflected. It was not accepted as a theory of science until research was carried out in a holistic way. In general, the development of literary critical views is associated with the name of connoisseurs of rhetoric. Plato, later Aristotle, proved his reflections on fiction, and their research was an important contribution to the development of literary criticism. Literary criticism, from Aristotle to Hegel, is presented in the form of aesthetics in a constant movement, and the work of art is studied in the form of a holistic structure. Works such as "Al-mo" jam", "Badoyi'us-Sanae' " played an important role in covering the history of the science of Oriental criticism. In the East, the value of the interpretation is high, and mentally strong scholars have coped with such an honorable, responsible task in the state of mind, savvy and passion. Each word, sign, gesture, interpretation and justification required great scientific potential. For example, in the Bible, the interpretation of the ending required a thorough knowledge of the language, an understanding of the meaning of the word, the possession of power presets, while other religious and secular works were reacted in similar ways. This is clearly confirmed by Ibn Sina's attitude to the comments made by Farabi to Aristotle's "metaphysics". Western criticism, on the other hand, focused mainly on text interpretation. In the process of text analysis, it can be understood that writing a foreword to a book, making annotations are the first examples of literary criticism.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Uzbek literary criticism first manifested itself in the press. Literary studies of each period show themselves in newspapers and magazines. The first examples of Uzbek literary criticism began to appear mainly in the press. Especially the Jadids showed enthusiasm in this field. The main goal of the Jadidism movement, the idea of raising people's consciousness, was mainly implemented through the press. During this period, A. Fitrat, A. Qadiri, A. Sa'di, Elbek explained their thoughts about literary studies. Of course, although the first critical articles cannot be called a deep scientific and theoretical study, these studies mark the first steps and the period of historical development of this field.

By the time of the Soviets, literary criticism had advanced considerably. But in the studies of this period, the examination of the work from the point of view of partisanship, classism, and viewing the work of art as a reflection of society became an important factor. Socialist realism was the fruit of this period. The price of the work is determined by these elements. In general, literary criticism is stereotyped. Although the volume of scientific research increased during the Shura period, sometimes it is felt that the socio-political requirements of the Shura period cannot be met. But despite this, during this period, literary studies made great achievements. The works, creativity, personality of writers and poets were widely, deeply and comprehensively studied, and the important role of creators in the development of our literature was justified. It should not be forgotten that the services of the above literary scholars were great in this place.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Despite the creation of many works related to the history of criticism in literary studies, a general methodology in this field has not yet come to the fore. So far, the only universally accepted rule in science is to study the history of criticism in connection with the main stages of the history of literature. The scientific and practical aspect of this direction is that it implies the parallel and continuous development of literature and works of art in the literary-historical process with literary criticism. It can be concluded from this that the main task of literary criticism is to analyze the work of one (or several) writers, artistic works as a special event in our literature, and on this basis, to raise, investigate, reveal and evaluate the issues that motivate the development of literature, as well as generalize consists of When it comes to literary criticism, it is appropriate to cite the following comments of Professor B. Karimov: "If there is a literary text, it means that it was its creator, receiver, mastery guide, guide. Whether in the East, in the West, now or in the past, the artistic text, its creation, reception, interpretation, analysis, evaluation, has a history. There is a work of art that is read, analyzed, interpreted. In this sense, Uzbek literary criticism is developing systematically. In the sources, the stages of development of Uzbek literature are dated differently. In particular, in the book "History of Uzbek Soviet literary criticism" (1987) it is dated as follows: 1. The emergence and first steps of Uzbek Soviet literary criticism; 2. Uzbek Soviet literary criticism is on the way to be armed with the aesthetics of socialist realism; 3. Uzbek literary criticism during the Great Patriotic War; 4. Uzbek literary criticism of the period after the Great Patriotic War; 5. The beginning of a new stage in the history of literary criticism; 6. Literary criticism to enter the path of rapid and wide development; 7. Uzbek literary criticism is at a new stage.

DISCUSSION

From the above periodization, it can be seen that the division into stages is not based on the growth of the literary critical process, but on political changes in society. Many of our literary experts had different views on the chronology of the development stages of Uzbek literary criticism. In this regard, while A. Rasulov and N. Khudoyberganov paid attention to its history and formation as a science, V. Rahmonov divided it into "modernism", "shura" and the "next period". S. Sadiq also recommended dividing the development of criticism into four stages. B. Nazarov, A. Rasulov also periodized criticism in four stages and explained the reasons for periodization.

Based on the above stages of development, our research includes periods of renewal stages of Uzbek literary criticism. It seems that since the 80s, the attitude towards works in Uzbek

literary criticism has changed a little and old traditions have been preserved. The main goal of our research is to study the transverse trends in criticism in the 1980s (which do not lead to renewal) and the researches that have been renewed in Uzbek literary criticism since the 1990s.

CONCLUSION

In Uzbek literary criticism, the 80s is a period that requires special study. During this period, the opportunity to withdraw from the ideology of the Shura and to express one's opinion was slightly expanded. Nevertheless, the inability to get rid of the old traditions did not disappear. In each period of literary criticism, the possibility of genres expands or researchers begin to create in the same genre. The 80s saw the development of the literary portrait genre. "In the 1960s and 1980s, effective results were achieved in the literary portrait genre. For example,S.Mamajonov "Ghayratiy", M. Mahmudov and V. Mahmudov "Ibrahim Rahim", L. Qayumov "Zulfiya", A. Abdusamatov "Habibi", Sh. Otaboev "Mirzakalon Ismaili", S. Sirojiddinov's portraits such as "Abdulhamid Majidi" are among them. According to the scholars who have studied these studies, although the genre of literary portraiture has developed, the portraits have been described dryly. Limitation with thoughts about the writer's personality and works is high, creative fantasy, interpretation of the text of the work seems shallow. In the 80s, along with the genre of literary portraits, critical-biographical essays also developed. "In the collection of literary-critical articles such as "Literature and Time" and "Mirror of Life" published in the 80s, critical-biographical essays were published under the headings "Literary portraits" and "Literary portrait drawings".

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